

AI: Artificial Intelligence, or perhaps Idiocy?

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The AI discussion has been around for quite a while, as was AI in some form or another. This, however, is not a story whether robots and computers will take over the world, but a personal observation inspired by something I find rather perplexing.

Recently I had a conversation with my colleague; someone I've worked successfully with for many years; practically a friend. We are both engaged in the world of Content Strategy and Copy-writing, having many projects behind us. Yet, something I heard coming from her left me flabbergasted, especially when knowing how professional, educated and intellectual she is:

“AI has already become more intelligent than us (humans).”

Statements of this kind could be seen as standard occurrence in Social Media or a over a beer talk. But this was not expressed as a joke nor an attempt of trolling. We still lack clear definitions of what human intelligence is, and yet, somehow, Artificial Intelligence has overgrown the very minds that created it. This would, of course, depend on the method how one defines intelligence. Does AI have infinite access to data? By all means. Does it posses perpetual processing power? Undoubtedly. Nonetheless, even the most sophisticated algorithm operates on a set of rules dictated by the source code, and consequently suffers limitations. Human mind, though heavily influenced by social norms, individual and environmental impacts, has no such boundaries in place.

My colleague then proceeded to double down saying that:

“AI has mastered creativity.”

and

“Exciting times are ahead, where AI will essentially make decisions for us.”

We are physically inferior to our primate ancestors in effectively every way. Chimpanzees are far stronger, more agile and resilient. Yet, during the long evolution process, we sacrificed the power of flesh for the growth of intellectual capacity. Call it intelligence if you will. Furthermore, in a world defined by limitations, borders and norms, the only essential and undisputed freedom left is to use this intellectual capacity as we see fit. In other words, to think is something no one can take away from you, and something that defines who you really are — A human being. Once we give up our minds to the algorithm, will there even be a purpose to live? Shall we turn into a meaningless blob of bone, flesh, fat and skin? After all, AI can do everything quicker and better... right?

I am not judging my colleague though. She is, like many of us, fascinated with progress. AI has shown immense potential in the fields of predictive maintenance, machine learning and deep learning alike. When talking about industry and technology, facts and benefits are obvious. On the other hand, while I have no doubt that the algorithm can write a piece of text in a fraction of the time it takes me to do it, generate an image which could very well be mistaken for art, or compose a very catchy tune, it should never be placed on the same level with human creativity. Why? Arts of the visual, word and melody remain our brightest achievements since the dawn of time. They represent our dreams, desires, fears and all other emotions that do not derive from the source code. Once we let semiconductors build our heritage, it is the moment when we cease to exist.

Finally, I will restrain from using AI in any form when writing, even at the price of having my content littered with spelling mistakes, grammatical errors and stylistic gaffes. We might aim for perfection, but perfect we are not, nor will ever become. From now on, everything I publish will contain the following statement:

This text was not generated, edited or proofread by the algorithm.